

Application Impulse Open Science Communities-NL

1. General information

Project title	Impulse Open Science Communities-NL
Applicant institution	SURF
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Accelerating Open Science through bottom-up community engagement - a national Executive Team for OSC-NL

Anna van 't Veer, Chair of the OSC-NL Board; Leiden University

In the Netherlands it is recognized that the transition towards an open academic culture requires a lively network of Open Science Communities (OSC-NL) focusing on peer-to-peer learning of OS principles and practices. In this proposal, the OSC-NL Board suggests to install an **OSC-NL Executive Team** that supports them, working on:

1. Improved knowledge exchange, community management and sustainability of our local OSCs
2. professionalising the network
3. expansion of the network

This investment will act as a multiplier on current investments in local OSCs and will accelerate the transition to OS from the bottom-up.

Het versnellen van Open Science via bottom-up community engagement - een landelijk uitvoerend team voor OSC-NL

Anna van 't Veer, voorzitter van OSC-NL; Universiteit van Leiden

In Nederland wordt erkend dat de overgang naar een open academische cultuur een levendig netwerk van Open Science Communities (OSC-NL) vereist, gericht op kennisuitwisseling tussen onderzoekers onderling, op het gebied van OS-principes en -praktijken. In dit voorstel stelt het OSC-NL-bestuur voor om een uitvoerend team in te stellen dat hen ondersteunt, en zorgt voor:

1. verbeterde kennisuitwisseling, community management en duurzaamheid van lokale OSC's
2. professionalisering van het netwerk
3. uitbreiding van het netwerk

Deze investering zal als katalysator fungeren voor de huidige investeringen in de lokale OSC's, en de overgang naar OS versnellen vanaf de werkvloer zelf.

2. Description of intended activities

Despite the increasing availability of Open Science (OS) infrastructure and the rise in policies to change behaviour, OS practices are not yet the norm. While pioneering researchers are adopting and developing OS practices, the majority of the academic community sticks to the status quo. We must engage this majority in order to make OS the new norm. Theories on culture change state that for the majority of researchers, behavioural change is driven by the prevailing norms and practices in their community (e.g., [Nosek et al. 2022](#)). These norms and practices can only be encouraged through peers; this is why local bottom-up Open Science Communities (OSCs) are crucial in the transition to OS. This need for bottom-up Open Science Communities is also highlighted in the Netherlands National Open Science Programme 2030 Ambition Document¹:

'Make Open Science normative through active Academic Community Engagement:

The transition towards an open academic culture requires lively networks of Open Science Communities of academics, support staff and interested non-academics in different domains, both national and international, to create awareness of the Open Science principles and practices.'

Currently, the Netherlands houses 12 Open Science Communities, one in each university city, bringing together over 2000 members across the country. Started by local researchers in Utrecht, these communities are places where researchers, educators, support staff, students and citizens are welcome to learn from each other how to put OS to practice. Over the years, local OSCs have organised a plethora of events and activities to make OS practices more visible and accessible at their institutions, ranging from workshops, symposia, barcamps, blogs, awards and newsletters to social media campaigns. By repeatedly showcasing how colleagues put OS into practice, OS becomes more normative. And by making these practices easily accessible through peer-to-peer knowledge exchange, OSCs effectively stimulate the transition to a culture change towards OS. Moreover, local OSCs collaborate with institutional programs and initiatives, provide input to policies, services and infrastructure, expressing the needs and opportunities as experienced by researchers.

Together, as the [OSC-NL](#) network, the Dutch OSCs have a shared mission and vision, code of conduct and onboarding tutorials. The network is governed by the OSC-NL board, consisting of eight (former) managers of local OSCs. The OSC-NL Board is responsible for all central decisions of OSC-NL and has three aims:

1. Foster local OSCs through knowledge exchange and tailored support

To stimulate community engagement and outreach of local OSCs, we exchange knowledge amongst each other. For instance, we share our success stories and failures, good practices and materials.

2. Provide input to policy, infrastructure and services on a national level

OSC-NL vocalizes the opportunities and needs of those who put OS to practice. By interacting with national stakeholders, we provide input to policy, infrastructure and services.

3. Contribute to a global culture change towards OS

OS is a global endeavour. Which is why OSC-NL has a leading role in the International Network of Open Science and Scholarship Communities (INOSC), the international counterpart of OSC-NL.

OpenScienceNL has recognized the crucial role of OSC-NL and recently committed targeted funding for the local OSCs for the coming three years, which most universities/OSCs intend to use to reimburse their local OSC community manager for ca. 0,2 FTE. However, the success of OSC-NL as a network depends on continued network maintenance by the volunteers in the OSC-NL Board; their leadership, outreach, and capacity to bring people together. This is recognised by OpenScienceNL, who state that:

'at present, OSC-NL lacks funding to carry out its work properly, let alone expand further. Activities are now mainly carried out on a volunteer basis. Ideally, at national level, a network is perpetuated to initiate and coordinate activities from which all local OSCs can benefit from.'

¹ Page 13, Open Science 2030 in the Netherlands: NPOS2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433767>

OSC-NL is grateful that OpenScienceNL is willing to foster the OSC-NL network on the national level. The plan as laid out in this application aims to install an **OSC-NL Executive Team (ET)**, that supports and operates under the governance of the OSC-NL Board. This team contributes to the realisation of the three aims of the network listed above.

Figure 1: The new ET will operate under the governance of the OSC-NL Board, who represent local OSCs.

Having an ET in place will allow the OSC-NL Board to effectively foster and sustain local OSCs. This will accelerate and multiply the impact of the national funding already received for local OSCs. Support of the OSC-NL ET for local OSCs will lead to an increase in visibility, knowledge transfer and uptake of OS practices, since that is where OS peer-to-peer knowledge transfer takes place. Moreover, the ET will help to professionalise the network and prepare the expansion of the network and its activities, thus empowering the ‘invisible leaders’ who are currently volunteering their free time to coordinate advancing OS practices.

Applicant Institution

SURF, the cooperative association of Dutch educational and research institutions, has agreed to host the OSC-NL ET and take on the role as applicant institution for this proposal. This aligns very well with the current SURF strategy which includes an active ‘Innovation Zone Enabling Open Science’. As the cooperative network organisation for research and education in the Dutch landscape, SURF can efficiently strengthen the activities of OSC-NL. SURF already cooperates with local and thematic Digital Competence Centers (DCCs), the DCC-PO (for the applied sciences), research libraries and other research communities on the national level. Other national communities hosted by SURF include the National Coordination Point Research Data Management (LCRDM). SURF also participates in several international networks that promote OS (such as the [Knowledge Exchange](#) initiative) and is the national mandated organisation for the EOSC. Like in recent years, OSC-NL can use the SURF offices for national meetings in centrally located Utrecht, and SURF will provide an extra member to the OSC-ET on an in-kind basis.

The Executive Team

The four potential ET members bring in a broad supplementary skill set:

Loek Brinkman (DANS), is a project manager and former researcher, who was (co)founder of the first OSC, has set up the international OSC Incubator Programme, and is vice-chair of the International Network of Open Science Communities;

Rianne Fijten (Maastricht University) is a senior researcher and (co)founder of OSC Maastricht (OSCM), represents the OSCM within INOSC and serves as an OSC-NL Board-member;

Tanya van Goch (SURF) co-leads the international [Knowledge Exchange Open Access Expert Group](#) and is community manager for the Enabling Open Science Innovation Zone at SURF;

Melanie Imming (Imming Impact) is a strategic OS consultant with experience in governance models and concept development of engagement related projects and events, eg. the [National OS Festival](#).

Together they have years of experience in community engagement in OS and are well-connected to (inter) national stakeholders in OS. They are all fully endorsed by the OSC-NL Board.

Below you will find a work plan for the coming four years, based on the given four elements that were required by OpenScienceNL:

WP 1. Networking

WP 2. Knowledge management

WP 3. Increase visibility and findability of local Open Science Communities and open science expertise

WP 4. Organisational embedding and perpetuation of OSC-NL after the project period (sustainability)

Each task within the WPs is led by one member of the Executive Team. This person is responsible for the objectives, but all tasks will be a collective effort of the entire ET.

We turned these four elements into work packages with corresponding deliverables:

Figure 2: GANTT chart of deliverables. Please note that, as (inter)national developments regarding Open Science are turbulent and not easy to predict, the planning of in particular the latter half of the project may be subject to change to remain agile and able to respond to unexpected development in the field.

WP1. Networking (10 PM)

One of the aims of this proposal is to ensure there are central resources in place to professionalise the network and prepare its expansion. The networking activities of the ET in the coming years can be described at three levels: local, national and international:

1.1 Local: OSC Community Management Toolkit - Local Stakeholder Engagement resources and tailored Incubator Program (4 PM)

The ET will set up an “OSC Community Management Toolkit” for all OSCs, a collection of expert formats and guidelines on specific procedures, skills, knowledge, and information such as to improve and professionalise various aspects of their community. At a recent OSC-NL Knowledge Exchange meeting, many OSCs have expressed interest in such a toolkit. It will be updated continuously. This toolkit will build upon the existing [OSC Starter Kit](#) and materials developed for the [OSC Incubator Program](#), which have previously developed to assist colleagues in setting-up their own OSC.

- 1.1.1 Add resources to this toolkit about Stakeholder Engagement: how to engage and interact with local stakeholders, such as university libraries and institutional OS programmes (if available).
- 1.1.2 Provide onboarding and/or connecting new OSCs at Dutch research institutes beyond those who are currently part of the OSC-NL network (e.g., the Open University, Universities of Applied Sciences, NWO-I and KNAW institutes). For this purpose, OSC-NL can benefit from existing strong SURF connections with these institutions
- 1.1.3 A dedicated and tailored run of the OSC Incubator Program, a 12-week online training program, will be offered to existing OSCs (year 1) and new OSCs (year 2).

1.2 National: Advocacy and policy (4 PM)

The OSC-NL ET will interact with national stakeholders to coordinate how OSC-NL can provide input to policy, infrastructure and services. Maintaining ties with policymakers and organising feedback from the network is crucial, as it will allow the communities to enable their members to provide input to national policies, research infrastructures and support services, to shape the transition to OS in accordance with researchers’ needs and workflows.

- 1.2.1 Liaise with national OS stakeholders, e.g. by contributing to events and ensuring OSC-NL Board or other members partake in advisory boards, e.g. of the National Thematic Digital Competence Centres (TDDCs), LCRDM, The Dutch Reproducibility Network (NLRN)¹, Science Communication Association (SciComNL), Research Software Community, Citizen Science Network NL, research funders (NWO, ZonMW, OpenScienceNL), Students for Open Science (SIOS), association of Universities (UNL), Medical Centers (NFU), Universities of Applied Science (VH), University Libraries (UKB) and service providers such as SURF, DANS and the eScience Center for research software. OSC-NL already has good relationships with most of these parties, but participation in advisory boards is now often decided on an ad hoc basis. We need to professionalise (prioritisation) procedures and good coordination of this investment of scarce resources.
- 1.2.2 Additionally, we will formalise instruments (e.g., an online OSC-NL Forum) to streamline communication and interaction between OSC-NL members and national stakeholders, to provide solicited and unsolicited input to policies and plans regarding all aspects of OS. For this, the OSC-NL ET will build upon prior experiences with gathering input amongst OSC-NL members, e.g. to the NPOS Ambition Document and NPOS Rolling Agenda.

1.3 International: INOSC (2 PM)

As (open) science does not stop at the border, international collaboration is key to realise the transition to OS. OSC-NL is part of - and a driving force in - the International Network of Open Science and Scholarship Communities (INOSC). While the focus of the OSC-NL ET is at the national and local levels, they support INOSC by engaging with international stakeholders and funding opportunities to create capacity for a future INOSC Executive Team. This approach is in line with the OpenScienceNL work program 2024-2025, which stresses the

¹ OSC-NL has a fruitful collaboration with NLRN, which we describe [here](#).

importance of connecting OSC-NL with both national and international network such as INOSC, and also in line with the UNL OS Agenda, which, besides stressing the importance of OSC-NL in making OS normative, highlights the importance of international collaboration in this regard.

Deliverables

- 1.1.1 OSC Community Management Toolkit - Local Stakeholder Engagement Resources (year 1 and continuously updated) **Lead: Rianne Fijten**
- 1.1.2 Connecting and onboarding of institutes to OSC-NL (continuously, target based on initial stakeholder mapping) **Lead: Tanya van Goch**
- 1.1.3 NL specific run of the Incubator Programme (year 1 and 2) **Lead: Loek Brinkman**
- 1.2.1 Stakeholder engagement plan focusing on OSC-NL participation in Advisory Boards (year 1) **Lead: Melanie Imming**
- 1.2.2 OSC-NL Forum project plan (year 1) and implementation (year 2) **Lead: Melanie Imming**
- 1.3 Recommendation for funding opportunities for future INOSC Executive Team (year 3) **Lead: Loek Brinkman**

WP2. Knowledge management (10 PM)

To mobilise a critical mass of scholars to achieve the OS cultural change, one of the key elements of the OSC-NL strategy is to showcase how researchers are currently implementing OS (visibility) and stimulating peer-to-peer knowledge exchange regarding those practices (accessibility), at the local level. In recent years, we have seen that this strategy is most successful for the target audience of OSCs: **the early and late majority of researchers engaging with OS**. Therefore, the OSC-NL ET will first and foremost support local OSCs to stimulate knowledge sharing. We will provide support for the managers of local OSCs in making their local OSCs flourish with the following activities:

2.1 OSC Community Management Toolkit - Knowledge Exchange Resources (3.5 PM)

We will add resources to our Toolkit about Knowledge Exchange which will include templates and worked examples of effective formats and strategies (e.g., workshops, symposia, hackathons on various OS topics).

2.2 Knowledge exchange sessions for coordinators of local OSC (1.5 PM)

- 2.2.1 We will build upon our very positive recent experience with the (one-off) [OSC-NL Knowledge Exchange session](#), which was organised as part of the OSC-NL project funded by a NWO OS Fund (ends aug 2024). These knowledge exchange sessions will be complemented with short workshops to upskill various aspects of community management as part of the knowledge exchange sessions.
- 2.2.2 The OSC-NL ET liaises with the INOSC Board to stimulate knowledge exchange sessions amongst managers of all OSCs of INOSC, where OSC-NL community managers can share experiences with and learn from OSC community managers abroad.

2.3 Tailored 1-on-1 support (3 PM)

In support of the local Dutch OSCs, the ET will offer 1-on-1 sessions with each OSC that are tailored to the challenges and opportunities that this specific OSC faces. This support will take place during 2-hour online sessions, during which the ET and the OSC representative will formulate recommendations based on the OSC Community Management Toolkit described above. Three months after this session, another brief session is planned as a follow-up, which allows the participants to evaluate progress and correct course where necessary. Overall, we will facilitate 10 of these sessions per year. In addition, we will also organise online follow-ups with OSCs after each knowledge exchange session (see 2.2.1).

2.4 (Inter)national events and projects (2 PM)

An important method for the OSC-NL network to ensure people know about the network, get interested in the ideas behind OS and open methods, and start putting OS to practice is to contribute to events from national stakeholders, as well as the organisation of our own national events and specific projects. For the latter, one can think of events such as an OSC-NL Barcamp and a bi-annual week long [OSC-NL OS Retreat](#), but also hackathons or hybrid sprints on specific OS topics. For instance, at the moment we are involved in organising a

National OSC-NL Open Science Week, after several local OSCs asked the Board to take this week—which is often already locally organised—to the national level.

Overall criteria for the Board to actually take up these specific projects are that they should enable **OSC-NL members, OS experts and newcomers to OS** to meet up, share knowledge and inspire each other, ensuring that participants can:

- learn from OS peers in different stages of their career, share insights and experiences in OS and build valuable collaborations;
- engage in thought-provoking discussions about the challenges and opportunities in implementing OS practices;
- participate in hands-on teams to develop practical skills in OS methodologies, tools, and more.

These kinds of Initiatives have already proven to be very effective in tapping into new cohorts of OS talent, and reaching out to people who are interested in OS but not yet actively engaged. However, these are time-consuming to organise and almost impossible to do this on a voluntary basis. To support the process of organising these projects in the future, the OSC-NL ET can:

- gather ideas from the OSC-NL community;
- subsequently prepare a short project proposal for ideas that the OSC-NL Board thinks are viable;
- If needed, apply for funding to organise these, as has been done earlier with e.g. the [OS Retreat](#);
- (find people who can) take on the organisation in addition to the regular ET work;
- Provide OSC-NL branded promotional materials that can be easily adjusted.

Deliverables

- 2.1. OSC Community Management Toolkit - Knowledge Exchange Resources (year 1 and continuously updated) **Lead: Loek Brinkman**
- 2.2.1 OSC-NL knowledge exchange sessions and workshops (2 per year) **Lead: Loek Brinkman**
Co-lead: Tanya van Goch
- 2.2.2 INOSC knowledge exchange sessions (1 per year) **Lead: Loek Brinkman**
- 2.3 Report of 1-on-1 support for local OSCs (1 per year) **Lead: Loek Brinkman**
- 2.4.1 Project plans and applications for funding for specific projects (continuously, ad hoc basis)
Lead: Melanie Imming/Rianne Fijten
- 2.4.2 Organisation of a National Barcamp as a satellite event to the National OS Festival (year 1)
Lead: Melanie Imming

WP3. Increase visibility and findability of local Open Science Communities and open science expertise (5 PM)

Within the network, internal communication channels are in place, such as a Slack channel for all OSC local managers, mailing groups, regular Board Meetings and weekly standups. These will be regularly updated according to the needs of the network. In addition to the efforts aimed at professionalising knowledge exchange mentioned above, the OSC-NL ET will work on delivering the following points to increase the visibility and findability of local OSC's and expertise:

3.1 OSC Community Management Toolkit - Visibility and findability resources (3 PM)

We will add resources to our OSC Toolkit about creating visibility and findability, which will include:

- Guidelines for effective communication;
 - Advice on how to publish OSC outputs as FAIR as possible;
 - Relevant OSC Branding formats such as social media images, posters, flyers, slides, stickers and gadgets;
- Additionally, all local OSC's have a website, and there is a shared national OSC-NL website. After our recent knowledge exchange meeting, it became apparent that a lot of the local communities want to update their websites. In order not to let everyone reinvent the wheel, we will share advice and templates for specific elements of the local websites, such as automated member lists, as part of the toolkit.

3.2 OSC-NL online presence (1 PM)

We will make the toolkit-resources developed in this project accessible and available in a FAIR way (e.g., with a DOI and a CC BY licence) and point to these from the OSC-NL website in a structured manner. Additionally, we will develop a social media strategy that will be distributed amongst the local OSCs that enables us to connect with both OS enthusiasts and the majority that we aim to reach. Elements within this social media strategy include pilot testing of various social media output such as blogs, posts on platforms such as Mastodon or BlueSky, but also less conventional media like podcasts or short videos. Topics will include new OSC-NL resources, as well as sharing important news and events that researchers should be aware of.

3.3 Connect our outputs and event calendars to platforms like [Taxila](#); (1 PM)

We will connect our websites to platforms like Taxila, that aim to give an overview of OS training, events and resources, e.g. via widgets, and will add resources on which open platforms one can use to share outputs in the tool kit.

Deliverables:

- 3.1 OSC Community Management Toolkit - (online) Visibility and findability resources (year 1 and continuously updated) Lead: **Rianne Fijten**
- 3.1.1 OSC Website checklist (year 2) Lead: **Rianne Fijten**
- 3.2 A targeted social media strategy that enables contact with both OS enthusiasts and those that are hesitant about OS (year 4). Lead: **Rianne Fijten** Co-lead: **Tanya van Goch**
- 3.3 OSC-NL coverage on Taxila: ensure all communities' events are scraped and all trainers and materials are included (year 1) Lead: **Tanya van Goch**

WP4. Organisational embedding and perpetuation of OSC-NL after the project period (sustainability) (5 PM)

4.1 OSC-NL governance model (2 PM)

OSC-NL became a Dutch foundation in December 2022. The OSC-NL governance model needs to be updated and professionalised. The ET will develop a Governance Model which will include rules and regulations (e.g., duration and terms of appointment of Board membership, clear responsibilities for the ET and the administrator ('penvoerder') organisation; possibly establishing Working Groups). The idea is to also include an Advisory Board next to the OSC-NL Board, and it needs to be explored whether a Member Council would be beneficial. If these are included in the Governance Model, the ET will coordinate the instalment of these new bodies.

4.2 OSC-NL sustainability (3 PM)

All 16 signatories of the OpenScienceNL covenant have agreed that it is key to strengthen local bottom up communities and specific national coordination teams¹. The OSC-NL ET will work together with OpenScienceNL to ensure objective 0.5 of the National Ambition document will be met:

'In 2025, all Open Science Communities (OSCs) are thriving, and form an entry point of research community engagement for NPOS actions. The scope of OSCs has extended beyond academia and includes all research performing organisations (e.g. Universities of Applied Sciences). There is structural financial support available to warrant the capacity for community building and community management in a sustainable manner'.²

The organisational embedding and financial sustainability of local OSCs is first and foremost the responsibility of local institutions, which is also reflected in the OS Agenda of UNL³. The OSC-NL ET will stimulate this process by assisting local OSCs in formulating a Sustainability Plan and a Monitoring Plan, with guidance as part of the OSC Community Management Toolkit and by writing these plans together in the Incubator Programme (see

¹ Page 17, OS 2030 in the Netherlands: NPOS2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433767>

² Page 30, Open Science 2030 in the Netherlands: NPOS2030 Ambition Document and Rolling Agenda.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7433767>

³ Section 1.3 Association of Universities in the Netherlands. (2023). Open Science Agenda UNL.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10362465>

also mentioned under “networking”). We will also organise special OSC-NL Knowledge Exchange sessions on how to liaise with local OS Programmes to work together on embedding the OSC locally, and lobby on behalf of OSC-NL to national stakeholders in OS.

Plans for the financial sustainability of the national coordination of the network shall be based on the support structures that will be implemented in the coming years, both on the local and national level. It is to be expected that the OSC-NL ET will remain relevant to foster OSC-NL after the duration of this project, albeit probably on a smaller scale. The OSC-NL ET will deliver a sustainability plan for the OSC-NL Board and ET in year 4. The plan will contain the criteria that are essential for sustainable coordination. The decision on which financial model is preferred remains at the institutions/signatories of the OpenScienceNL Covenant, therefore the plan will also include an estimation of the required resources and different funding scenarios.

Deliverables:

- 4.1 Governance Model for OSC-NL (year 1) and the instalment of possible new governance bodies that stem from the new model **Lead: Melanie Imming**
- 4.2.1 OSC Toolkit - Sustainability and monitoring resources (year 1 and continuously updated)
Lead: Rianne Fijten
- 4.2.2 OSC-NL ET sustainability plan - initial version (year 3) **Lead: Rianne Fijten**
- 4.2.3 OSC-NL ET sustainability plan - final version (year 4) **Lead: Rianne Fijten**

3. Financial information

3.1 Personnel costs (HOT tariffs)

Description	UFO-profile	HOT scale	Salary (€)	Hourly rate (HOT)	Total hours	Total (€)
<i>Role</i>		<i>(Scale according to HOT tariffs)</i>				
Dr. Loek Brinkman	Project Manager	█	█	█	1290 (10 PM)	█
Dr. Rianne Fijten	Assistant Professor	█	█	█	1290 (10 PM)	█
Drs. Tanya van Goch	NA	NA			600 (4 PM)	In-kind SURF
Drs. Melanie Imming*	Senior programme manager	NA		█ (Reduced rate)	775 (6 PM)	█
Total					3180	349.715

*Please note that in the original application, the services of Melanie Imming were listed under '3.2 Other costs' as third-party service. To provide a more comprehensive overview of all personnel involved, we have included those costs here in 3.1

3.2 Other costs

Description	Explanation	Costs (€)
Communication tools	Development and hosting OSC NL websites, OSC Forum, other GDPR proof (registration) tool.	8.000
	Design and production of printed and online materials (including promotional materials)	10.000
Travel budget (intern)	Travel costs	5.000
Participation symposia / events, etc.	Production of materials like video(s), posters and roll ups	11.285
	Reimbursement OSC-NL members or external speakers who participate in/organise sessions/events/projects/governance bodies of OSC-NL	11.000
Audit	Audit by external accountant (mandated)	5.000
Total		50.285

3.3 Total costs

Category	Total (€)
<i>Personnel costs</i>	349.715
<i>Other costs</i>	50.285
Total	400.000

4. Statements and signature

Other financing

No Yes

OSC-NL has received a 50K grant from the OS Fund that runs until sept 2024, from which we were able to fund an in-person and an online Knowledge Exchange session for our OSC managers, community management training for 6 Board members and an Open Science Retreat open to everyone interested in OS and 0,1 fte for the Chair of the Board. (See [here](#) for the full proposal)

By submitting this form, I declare that

I have completed this form truthfully;

I declare on behalf of the institution that the project will comply with the nationally and internationally accepted standards of scientific conduct as stated in the Dutch Code of Conduct for Scientific Integrity ([Nederlandse Gedragscode Wetenschappelijke Integriteit](#))

Name and initials:

Dr. Anna van 't Veer, Chair OSC-NL

Place: Leiden

Date: March 14th, 2024

Dr. Loek Brinkman, vice-Chair OSC-NL

Place: Leusden

Date: March 14th, 2024

Jet de Ranitz, Chair board of directors, SURF

Place: Utrecht

Date: March 14th, 2024